

House as Home

Emotions Centred Design for Disability

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Abstract: In this paper we highlight how current approaches to design for disability have failed to consider the emotional needs not only of those with disabilities but their families and other carers as well. In conjunction with this, we demonstrate through a review of literature the significance of the house, the home and home in the support and growth of the person as a whole in association with their loved ones, and the potential inequity that arises when the emotional and holistic dimensions of ‘being’ are neglected. With a growing trend nationally and internationally away from group and shared housing, a greater focus on the family and their home is required. However, as research has shown, home for families where a family member has a disability is not necessarily a positive experience; it can be a source of stress, work, conflict and burden, arousing emotions ranging from loss of control through to guilt. As proposed in the paper, consideration of the negative as well as positive emotions demands exploration of the ‘middle ground’ between institutions and home-based care models. This paper outlines the beginning of one such exploration.

Key words: *Design, Disability, Emotion.*

1. Introduction

Traditionally, design undertaken for individuals with a disability, and those closest to them, has focused largely on the physical environment and how to meet specific functional needs. While volumes have been written on creating environments that best support the day-to-day ergonomic requirements of people with disabilities, comparatively little research has gone into the emotional qualities of the spaces we call ‘home’ and how these apply to houses where individuals with disability reside and are cared for.

This paper is written in relation to a project and case study that seeks to address this omission. The project involves Kyabra, a not-for-profit organization, the DIA Design Action Group, a pro-bono design practice group and the Queensland University of Technology, working together to design a more holistic, emotionally sustainable independent living model of housing for families where a member of the family has a disability. The authors of this paper are researchers of the university as well as design practice members.

The initiative between all three organizations, entitled *Livingin*, seeks to address the currently unfulfilled needs of Kyabra’s client families with the aim of designing independent living options which not only address the

specific needs of each individual family, but also develops to form the foundation of a holistic model that considers simultaneously the physical environment, the psychosocial environment, and the system of care delivery. The first home that is being designed is for a family unit that comprises a 32-year-old woman with an intellectual disability (born with a large occipital encephalocele), vision and mobility problems, epilepsy, autistic tendencies and her parents who, in conjunction with government assistance, are responsible for providing the high levels of care needed for their daughter. The need to develop an independent living model for a large number of families such as these has stemmed, in part, from concern of the parents regarding the lack of appropriate housing options for their children as they approach an age where they will no longer be able to provide the high levels of 24-hour care required for their children.

In the following paper, we first look at some of the widely accepted psychological, social and existential qualities that are at play in the spaces we call 'home'. From here we explore how the reality of the experience of home can be significantly changed when it functions as both a care-giving setting for an individual with a disability and a home for a variety of inhabitants including the individual with a disability. It is against this backdrop that we then consider the current context and housing options for people with disability in Australia, reflect on the areas where the needs for 'home' are not currently being met, and describe the approach currently underway in developing an alternative housing and care provision model for independent living.

In doing this, we explicitly call into question the notion that the physical challenges associated with the care-giving environment are the most pivotal in determining whether or not a house or living space successfully becomes a 'home' to all of its inhabitants. Indeed, this appears to be the case when one takes a critical view of research on 'universal design' and the legislation and design guidelines informed by such research. One could even go as far to speculate that in an attempt to be inclusive and equitable the outcome is anything but, or at the very least compromised, when legislation, research and design continue to ignore the multitude of dimensions of human 'being' and their contribution both individually and collectively in terms of the family unit to a meaningful life.

As the following critique will highlight, questions can also be raised about the effect on the emotional and intellectual growth of a person with a disability when design attempts to produce environments devoid of the potential for personalisation and risk taking; again failing to afford a specific group of people the same opportunities as the general population.

...we are all - throughout our lives - striving toward a state of wholeness, of being wholly ourselves...the places we live in are reflections of that process, and indeed the places themselves have a powerful effect on our journey toward wholeness. [In addition],...we all play roles in each others' dramas: sometimes as lead, sometimes as supporting actor... [1].

2. Methodology

As indicated previously, the project is being undertaken by a 'collective' involving the community service provider (who is also the builder), a group of designers, and a university research team. In addition to providing an ethical and conceptual framework for informing the consensus design process, research also plays a role in enhancing the criticality and rigor of the project seeking a credible and enduring level of engagement and outcome. PhD students embedded in the project focus on certain aspects, for example, policy, design, sustainability and so on, considered chiefly from an interpretivist position while adopting particular

methodological lenses (for example, grounded theory, phenomenology) relevant to the questions being asked. In all, the project is regarded as a case study adopting an action research frame-of-reference.

In terms of this paper, the main areas of research focus were:

- Theoretical understanding of the emotional dimensions of dwelling through the notion of 'home',
- Historical data collection relating to the provision of care to individuals with disability both nationally and internationally,
- Inquiry into positive and negative aspects of the current care provision models and conceptual frameworks currently available, especially within the Australian context,
- Collation of information from the end users which identified areas of greatest need that had resulted from the current government and private systems at play

All data were collected from research publications, government and community organization reports and subjected to contextual and thematic analysis.

3. Results

3.1 Home

In reviewing literature on home there is considerable overlap and agreement about the attributes of home as a place that is something more than it being a space providing shelter and physical security for the occupants and their possessions. At its most basic, the experience of a home is rooted in the human ability to form specific and strong emotional attachments to place. Stedman [2] defines a sense of place attachment as "...a collection of symbolic meanings, attachment, and satisfaction with a spatial setting held by an individual or group". It is through these symbolic meanings and attachments that the simple person-environment interaction with a place or dwelling transforms into the more complex, and strongly emotive experience that we call 'home'. One can conceptualise of the transition of a space from dwelling or mere 'house' to a 'home' as a continuum that is travelled through the accumulation of experience. Stedman summarises this journey in the following way:

"...the people residing in a house (i.e. the physical structure with its spatial and sensory properties) can only begin to truly experience it as a home when meaningful attributes are assigned to their experiences, interactions and familiar routines in that house. The roles of people living in that house and relationships between them, as part of families or otherwise, also contribute to experiential attributes of living in that space".

The notion of home as a place of emotional security is captured in metaphors such as nest and cocoon evoking notions of nurturance, warmth, love and caring symbolically conveyed through various physical qualities of the house such as spatial layout and the proximity of the parent's bedrooms to young children's bedrooms or of objects within that are familiar and permanent [1]. In terms of bedrooms, Cooper-Marcus highlights the significance of having one's own bedroom or if this is not possible a space of one's own providing for control, privacy, personalisation and the fostering of independence, self-expression and self-actualisation. According to Cooper-Marcus houses should also be places of exploration and stimulation via daydreaming, fantasising, playing. Houses should have spaces where family members can undertake activities together reinforcing the notion of the family as a unit and associated feelings of relatedness and belonging.

The meaning that home has for a person can also change over their lifetime, with some attributes given more emphasis than others depending on age or circumstances (for example, divorce, death or disability). Studies involving elderly people show that many regard the home as an 'investment of a lifetime'; in other words a

tangible record of a family's investment [3]. Studies also show that in general people who own their own house experience, in spite of mortgage stress, greater satisfaction and well-being attributable to having greater control over a highly intimate environment; "...the most satisfying homes allow for control of territory by the individuals who live there" [4]. For some, the home is the embodiment of a deceased spouse their presence continuing to be felt through memories rekindled by particular objects, spaces, rituals associated with their loved one. Several discussed how remaining in one's home stood as a symbol of their ability to cope contributing to a continuing sense of worth and purpose [3]. Over the course of one's life then, the house as home remains as a powerful force.

Of course, home can also evoke negative feelings or not be totally responsive to a particular individual's needs due to the dynamics of those living there. "When one person in the family – mother, wife, husband [or child with special needs] – moulds a place in terms of their own environmental needs and biases, others – children, [siblings], spouse, lover – may find this place not at all supportive of their self identity" [1]. Home may also evoke conflicting feelings or ambivalence as Israel [4] describes it; such as when attachment is associated with mixed feelings of pain and pleasure, or vulnerability and entrapment. In providing limits to be transgressed and contradictions to be negotiated, home is also a setting for testing courage and personal growth [1]. In all, "the experience of home is at once the most primary of spatial meanings and ideologies. The meaning of house and home is founded upon a series of linked dialectic oppositions – home/journey; familiar/strange; inside/outside; safety/danger; order/chaos; private/public and identity/community" [5].

The reality that home is not always a positive experience is discussed by Wise [6] who advocates that it is crucial to separate ideas of 'home' and 'the home'. As indicated previously, 'the home' may have little to do with comfort in that it may be a space of pain with 'home' in this sense meaning a process of coping, comforting, stabilising oneself. "Home is not authentic or inauthentic; it does not exist a priori, naturally or inevitably. It is not individualistic. The relation between home and the home is always being negotiated..." [6].

3.2 When 'the home' is a care setting

While we have touched on a number of ways of conceptualising home in general, it is important to investigate further how these experiences of home can be changed when this environment becomes the site of care-giving for a person (child or adult) with disability. Despite considerable research being undertaken the focus has chiefly been on the individual with disability and their physical needs. However, as "care by adults to other adults is being increasingly transferred from formal public institutions to the private home" [7] we argue that there is a greater need to view the home caring environment from a more holistic perspective that incorporates all members of the household (both permanent and temporary). In support of this, Gulwadi [8] writes that "When it [the home] unpredictably becomes a care setting for a co-residing family member, there is a stress-inducing disruption of what is familiar and meaningful....in the overall emotional experience of 'home' experienced by it's occupants". In drawing attention to the ability of the built environment to either support or challenge the experience of home for it's inhabitants when care-giving is introduced, Gulwadi [8] asserts that "...the interplay of architectural, social and experiential components of a house in which care-giving occurs can intensify or diminish care-giving stress by changing the experienced meaning of home". Gulwadi uses research by Calasanti and Bowen to illustrate the fact that "a focus on the emotional responsibility of care-givers" [9] is comparatively rare in care-giving research.

A home in which care-giving occurs can easily become a source of both work and stress, especially in the case of carers required to work outside the home; a phenomenon often referred to as the “double day” or “dual burden”. Thus rather than serve as a sanctuary or place of restoration and refuge, the change in the experienced meaning of the environment can impact on all of its inhabitants negatively.

Given that there is a general agreement that “When the care-giver is overburdened, the consequences can be devastating for an entire family. The care-givers mental and physical health suffers, the interaction between family members suffers, and the quality of care suffers” [7] it is important to be cognisant of the potential for a vicious cycle to be formed where care-giver stress impacts on family members, reducing the quality of care and creating a cycle of stress for all the inhabitants of the house. Other researchers such as Grbich [10] describe the emotional strain of care-giving as a “burden of care” which “is seen as affecting the care-givers psyche and involves such emotions as resentment, embarrassment, overload, and feeling trapped, as well as confusion, loss, hopelessness and powerlessness. Feelings which dominate include anxiety, depression, emptiness, fear, helplessness, difficulty in getting on top of things, loss of control, uncertainty, resentment, anger and guilt” [10]. To further exacerbate the problem of the changed experience of a home, Gulwadi eloquently describes the phenomenon of increased focus on the home due to factors such as reduced mobility, social isolation, removal from the working sphere contributing to the care-giving home becoming the “centre of a shrinking universe” [8]. Gulwadi points out that “greater demands on the spatial and infrastructural adequacy of the dwelling unit, including its size and efficiency both for care-giving and for relating to others more and more from one’s own home base” [7]. Michelson and Tepperman [7] used time-use data to analyse care-giving activities in adults and their results uncovered that “...care-givers spend only half as much time in other people’s homes. Given the responsibility of care-giving, people spend more of their socializing time (and other activities) at home and not out in somebody else’s home” [7].

Another difference that can be witnessed in a family home where care-giving occurs is a disruption to the normal progressive changes to relationship patterns that occur between parent and child. In a traditional developmental sequence, one would generally see the increasing need for autonomy and privacy in children as they grow. Clare cooper Marcus in her book *House as Mirror of Self* describes the physical manifestations of this process that appear even in young children as the creation of a “home-away-from-home” [1]. From the building of cubby and tree houses through to the personalisation of a teenager’s room, this gradual separation of the child from the parental unit can be significantly upset by the need for continued and intensive care-giving. In some cases this process may even be seen to be reversed where, due to the disability, care-giving needs increase with time rather than subside. Where the disability is primarily physical, with psychological development proceeding relatively unimpeded, this becomes especially relevant. Little focus has been placed on design which addresses the emotional and social needs for both autonomy and privacy or indeed a ‘home away from home’ for both the parent and child.

One of the critical notions in looking at the experience of a home where care-giving occurs is that “a given setting will contain as many different meanings as there are people using the setting” [2]. What may be a place of refuge for one family member can be seen as a source of work or stress for another. Certainly it cannot be overstated that “...one persistent stressor is lack of space and time away from care-giving tasks..” [8]. Thus if one regularly encounters home as a site of work and stress, a disruption to normal familial patterns of relating, a site where a wide range of negative emotions from guilt through to anger are acted out in combination with a

lack of time spent outside the home participating in restorative activities such as socializing, this can create an overall experience that far and away overshadows any obstacles presented by the physical environment alone.

3.3 Current options available for housing individuals with disability – the Australian context

Australia, like many western nations has undergone significant changes in the way that those with disability live and are cared for in the past 50 years. Australia has seen a strong trend towards de-institutionalisation which “reflects beliefs that, for many problems, removal from the local community or home takes a person away from close personal relationships and supports and into a dehumanized setting subject more to institutional prerogatives” [7]. “Recent policy developments place emphasis on family-based support models designed to maintain people with disability in their family of origin. In Australia, government policy links the interests of the person with a disability with those of their family, and incorporates family-centered policies with person centered approaches to intervention” [11].

This shift in responsibility for the care of individuals with disability from the public to the private spheres, while addressing some of the less desirable conditions traditionally associated with institutionalised care, has in turn given rise to a new set of issues. While Australia has a government based universal health care system, the care of individuals with disability falls under the jurisdiction of a number of state and federal based government agencies. Due to regular changes in government policies at both levels, this current system with multiple agency involvement has been known to result in both ‘overlaps’ and also ‘gaps’ in the overall provision of care and options for accommodation.

In terms of non-institutionalised options, current provision includes: private rental, public housing rental or private home ownership either by the individual themselves or their family. Of course, the reality is there is little choice for many for a variety of reasons including severity of disability, lack of family support, and little or no financial security. Even for individuals being cared for by their families, there is little certainty that this will continue particularly with parent carers who are aging. Eventually, most will be forced at the very least into co-tenancy with another person with a disability. As highlighted by various community groups including the Community Safeguards Coalition [12] this practice is a direct contravention of Article 19(a) of the *United Nations Convention on the Human Rights of People with Disability*, which states:

Persons with disabilities have the opportunity to choose their place of residence and where and with whom they live on an equal basis with others and are not obliged to live in a particular living arrangement.

Negative impacts of forced co-tenancy include: failure to meet individual needs; loss of the right to make important lifestyle decisions due to the rigidity of routines and depersonalisation contributing to the compromise of psychological wellbeing and the development of behavioural issues; inadequate support due to cost-cutting; and increased vulnerability to abuse and neglect by the co-tenant or visitors [12]. Fundamentally, the aim of the coalition is for the relevant government departments to “ensure that control over the living arrangements of people with disability returns to the authority of people with disability and/or their families” [12]. In this respect, their main message is that “when people with disability take control of their housing and their lives, just like everybody else, they create better solutions” [12].

Information on the efficacy of the current support systems available to families where care-giving occurs comes from survey such as the ‘Family Needs Survey’ and are distributed and collated by a range of groups from

government bodies through to universities. A survey distributed by Bailey and Simeonsson pointed to the fact that “The most commonly identified community services needs were respite services and, to a lesser extent day support and 24-hour and emergency service” [11]. Other recent Australian research into current provisions for families where care-giving occurs does not point primarily to a request by families for more extraneous ‘homes’ or institutions to be built for family members to be relocated to, but rather, respite care is listed as one of the most primary needs. While the majority of carers in the ‘Family Needs Survey’ were already utilising some form of respite care, 47% expressed “ a need for more respite, cheaper respite, different types of respite, more regular respite, respite in greater “chunks”, respite in different environments, respite at different times, and greater flexibility in accessing this service” [11].

Given that “Respite care is potentially one important intervention to alleviate carer stress” [11] it is interesting that families are in some cases reporting not using available respite services due to a lack of suitable environments. Behaviours where families choose not to utilise desperately needed resources starts to point to the relative importance of the social and emotional aspects of the care-giving environment. When faced with the option of leaving children or adolescents in aged care facilities or invite strangers into their home to care, families are sacrificing their own mental and physical needs in order to avoid these potentially traumatic experiences.

3.4 Design for one, design for all?

De-institutionalisation of care for people with disabilities has resulted in a greater focus on the design of alternative forms of accommodation in order to make it accessible and functional and, for those using it, more independent. As is the case in most Western countries this has been informed largely by Principles of Universal Design developed in 1997 by the Center for Universal Design, North Carolina State University (1997). However, as Calkins [13] notes the vast majority of universal design applications have focused on people with physical impairments failing to address other impairments of a cognitive and/or affective nature. In our local context here the Queensland Government Department of Housing [14] has adopted the seven principles as follows:

Principle 1: Equitable Use

Principle 2: Flexible Use

Principle 3: Simple and Intuitive Use

Principle 4: Perceptible Information

Principle 5: Tolerance for Error

Principle 6: Low Physical Effort

Principle 7: Size and Space for Approach and Use

As well as addressing physical needs chiefly, these principles also aim to be relevant to as many people as possible and, in so doing, tend to be inadequate in specific situations [15]. For Webb & Williams [16] “ the confluence of design inefficacy and individual functional limitations perpetuate a disabling downward spiral of exclusion and functional loss that, at best, reduces quality of life and, at worst, dehumanizes” and so it is “necessary... to understand broader definitions of both disability (in people) and usability (in environmental design) in order to more fully understand the person-environment (P-E) interrelationship and the role of the built environment as an enabling device” [16].

The danger then of focusing solely on the physical impairments and trying to find a ‘universal’ answer to such

problems lies in the one-dimensional nature of this task. Certainly one can't be surprised if a one-dimensional approach that ignores the other layers of human experience and existence results in spaces that are experienced as equally naïve and flat. Ironically, the production of spaces which perfectly accommodate all the 'needs' of a person with disability often create care-giving settings that people do not want to use. To highlight an example of emotional factors outweighing physical, most of us can personally name a number of aging individuals who, when offered places in aged-care facilities immaculately designed to cater to all of their increasing physical needs, will fight to stay in far less 'suitable' environments which do accommodate their emotional and social desires.

After years of working with, researching and writing on disabilities and diseases Oliver Sacks [17] began to regard the process of individual adaptation to defects, disorders and diseases as carrying an inherent and paradoxical "creative potential". In his book *An Anthropologist on Mars*, he writes that:

Thus while one may be horrified by the ravages of developmental disorder or disease, one may sometimes see them as creative too – for if they destroy particular paths, particular ways of doing things, they may force the nervous system into making other path's and ways, force on it unexpected growth and evolution [17].

It is this process of adaptation and evolution in the way that we conceptualize, design and create homes for individuals with disabilities and those closest to them that carries with it enormous creative potential. This opportunity to examine and re-evaluate not only how a house can better suit the physical and instrumental needs (for example, the house as a financial investment), but more notably the psychological, social and aesthetic needs of all those that call it 'home' is one that has been borne from the current and distinct lack of suitable options currently.

3.5 A new model of independent living and design process

Unlike most private or government based projects, the not-for-profit community service provider described in this paper seeks to address the current lack of accommodation choices first and foremost from the perspective of the individual families participating. This particular vantage point places significantly more emphasis on the unique, physical, social and emotional needs of the actual families destined to call these spaces 'home' while still giving birth to a model that is relevant on a larger scale.

It is important to note that the combination of the pro-bono professionals, with the not-for-profit community group 'client' affords the team a unique position which is unconstrained by financial or government affiliated political drivers and agendas and frees them to approach the design task from a multitude of perspectives that are normally not entertained or viable in the commercial or government led projects. Rather than become an exercise in meeting a demographic 'gap' in a marketplace or government care-delivery model, designers are able to approach the task alongside the client collective and give equal if not greater commitment to the end users psychological and social experience of a 'home for life' [11], rather than a place of residence. The fact that this design process is being shared closely with the actual inhabitants (as opposed to the predicted user groups) adds further layers of meaning to the process as the user's engage in the "powerful experience of creativity, learning about self via moulding the physical environment" [1].

In relation to the research conducted in collaboration with this organization and described in this paper, it provides theoretical support for a focus on home and its emotive qualities; a focus that incorporates the entire

family and carers for whom the house and home is a care setting. It also provides support for the idea currently being tested that a single dwelling can be built which provides shifting levels of both privacy and connectivity over the course of the family's life. Indeed to take the familiar suburban concept of a family home on a single block of land and design it so that in its early days it can be a single home while later in the life of the family, as the parents and children age and develop, it can be easily converted to two dwellings, is a unique approach in Australia at this time. There are potentially great economic benefits associated with such a system, where as the parents as carers age, and may inevitably require care themselves or pass away, the adjoining dwelling can then be subsequently inhabited by an outside carer or rented out for income which funds the care of the grown child. The central idea in this model is that the home becomes a 'home for life' for all parties, that individuals are able to form lasting relationships and enact control over the place that is ultimately the centre of their universe. The idea is to seek to design places that accommodate both refuge and retreat, as well as social and emotional connection for both the individual with the disability and those caring for them and understand that these needs will change throughout the total lifespan of all parties.

4. Conclusions

In summary, this paper has highlighted how current approaches to design for disability have failed to consider the emotional needs not only of those with disabilities but their families and other carers as well. In conjunction with this, it has demonstrated through a review of literature the significance of the house, the home and home in the support and growth of the person as a whole in association with their loved ones, and the potential inequity that arises when the emotional and holistic dimensions of 'being' are neglected. As conveyed in the paper, there is a growing trend nationally and internationally away from group and shared housing necessitating a greater focus on the family and their home. However, as research has shown, home for families with disabilities is not necessarily always a positive experience; it can be a source of stress, work, conflict and burden, arousing emotions ranging from loss of control through to guilt. Daily dramas played out on this stage are potentially magnified due to the fact that lack of time spent outside the home means it is now the 'centre of a shrinking universe'. In response to this, the collective noted in this paper is looking to find a better solution outside the institutions and home-based care models by adopting an emotions centred design approach that has the 'home for life' as its goal. It is hoped that, looking beyond the final physical design produced by this project, if it can generate more consideration by the design community into the social and emotional factors of housing for individuals and families living with disability, this will result in a positive change to the way in which we approach the task of designing these spaces and result in more environments that people truly consider to be 'home'.

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5. References and Citations

- [1] Cooper-Marcus, C. (1995) *House as Mirror of Self*. Berkeley: Conari Press.
- [2] Stedman, R. C. (2002) Toward a social psychology of place: Predicting behavior from place-based cognitions, attitude, and identity. *Environment and Behavior*, 34 (5), 561-581.
- [3] Davison, B., Kendig, H., Stephens, F. & Merrill, V. (1993) *It's My Place*. Canberra: Australian Government Publishing Service.
- [4] Israel, T. (2003) *Some Place Like Home*. England: Wiley-Academy.
- [5] Dovey, K. (1999) *Framing Places*. London: Routledge.
- [6] Wise, J. M. (2000) Home: Territory and identity. In M. Taylor & J. Preston (Eds.), *Intimus* (pp. 391-396). England: Wiley-Academy.
- [7] Michelson, W. & Tepperman, L. (2003) Focus on home: What time-use data can tell about care-giving to adults. *The Journal of Social Issues*, 59 (3), 591.
- [8] Gulwadi, G. B. (2002) Restorative home environments for family caregivers. *Journal of Aging Studies*. 23 (3), 197-204.
- [9] Calasanti, T. & Bowen, M. E. (2006) Spousal caregiving and crossing gender boundaries: Maintaining gendered identities. *Journal of Aging Studies*, 20 (3), 253-263.
- [10] Grbich, C., Parker, D. & Maddocks, I. (2001) The emotions and coping strategies of care-givers of family members with a terminal cancer. *Journal of Palliative Care*, 17 (1), 30-3.
- [11] Burton-Smith, R., McVilly, K. R., Yazbeck, M., Parmenter, T. R. & Tsutsui, T. (2009) Service and support needs of Australian carers supporting a family member with disability at home. *Journal of Intellectual & Developmental Disability*, 34 (3), 239.
- [12] Community Safeguards Coalition Position Statement (2009) My Life, my home, my solution.
- [13] Calkins, M. P. & Marsden, J. P. (2000) Home is where the heart is: Designing to recreate home. *Alzheimer's Care Quarterly*, 1 (1), 8-16.
- [14] Queensland Government Department of Housing (2001) *Smart Housing 1 – Universal Housing Design*. Brisbane: Department of Housing.
- [15] Preiser, W.F.E. (2008) Universal design: From policy to assessment research and practice. *Archnet-IJAR International Journal of Architectural Research*, 2, (2), 78-93.
- [16] Webb, J. K. & Williams, B. T. (2007) Perceptions of independent living (IL): Influences on the relationship between disability and design. *IDRP Interdisciplinary Design and Research e-Journal*, 1 (1), 1-24.
- [17] Sacks, O. (1995) *An Anthropologist on Mars*. New York: Random House.